

Ethnic Dance And National Integration: The National Troupe Example

Chris Nwaru Ph.D

Department of Theatre Arts
Imo State University, Owerri
chrisnwaru@yahoo.com
08036720975

Abstract

Nigeria is made up of over 250 identified ethnic groups and had evolved systems and structures for governance before the advent of Islam, Christianity and Colonialism. These systems and structures were indigenous in concepts, forms and styles. All these indigenous cultures utilize dance profusely in their attempts to formulate, sustain and animate their cultural characters and world views. While ethnic differences have been fingered as the chief culprits that militate against unity in the body polity, it is apparent from the National Troupe's example that inter-ethnic integration had created a forum to code-switch to cultural experiences and practice that can enrich and further develop the Nigerian dance art. Therefore, this paper through the use of interview and content analysis concludes that the integration of ethnical dances by the National Troupe of Nigeria, the understanding and appreciation of cultural behaviours' other than one's have engendered mutuality which has led to dance development and national unity.

Keywords: Dance, National, Integration and National Troupe of Nigeria

Introduction

Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and culturally diverse society. The colonial masters had to amalgamate the diverse ethnicities that made up Nigeria by the British. Before the colonial masters came, different ethnic region had their traditional political and religious practices and institutions. These ethnic groups celebrate their

festivals depending on the period (rainy and dry season). They featured their traditional dances prominently in these festivals. Some dances were used to honour the gods and deities while others were used for recreational and occupational services. This paper expounds such conceptual issues as ethnicity, cultural diversity, and national integration. It is argued that the integration of the

ethnic/traditional dances in the National Troupe of Nigerian context has been an attempt to forge unity in diversity and development of the traditional dance. Therefore, there is the need to bring the diversified culture tighter into one cultural and national entity.

Traditional African Dance (Ethnic Dance)

Ethnic dance has to do with cultural or traditional dance and so in this paper, the word ethnic, cultural and traditional will be used interchangeably. In Nigeria and other parts of Africa, ethnic dance has always been an integral part of peoples' lives, and often manifests itself within various aspects of everyday life including work, play, and general belief systems. Always a dynamic art form in Africa dance is a pivotal activity for various families, ethnic groups and nations. The subject matter of ethnic dance according to Pearl Primus (1996, p.6),

Is all inclusive of every activity between birth and death – the seed which trembles to be born – the first breath of life – the growth, the struggle for existence - the ecstasy and sorrow which is life, and there the path back to the earth. This is the dance.

According to Hanna (1973), Africa has about 1,000 different languages, and probably has many dance patterns. Hanna noted that in

Africa, dance styles vary enormously as definitions of dance. For example, among the Igbo, Akan, Efik, Azande, and Kamba, dance involves and is closely associated with vocal and instrumental music, including the drum, which are theatrical elements. In contrast, among the Zulu, Matabele, Shi, Ngoni, Turkana, and Wanyaturu, drums are not used, and sometimes the users of drums are despised.

It may be difficult to define ethnic dance given the diversity of practices and activities associated with the term in Nigeria and on the African continent, but some of the characteristics observed by Hanna (1973), are helpful in establishing how ethnic dance is defined and how it will be used in this paper. The physical behavior of dancers is one of the main kinesthetic indicators in the traditional dance: the human body as an instrument of dance releases energy through muscular responses to stimuli. Social behaviour in traditional dance is also used to reflect the proxemics relationships among individuals in groups—and among groups.

The evolution of ethnic dance art in Africa may not differ greatly from its evolution in Europe, because in both regions, dance was a part and parcel of rituals and ritual sacrifices, festivals, and also was used in the worship of one god or

another by individuals and communities making supplications for good health, wealth, children and peace in the society. The origin of traditional (ethnic) dances in Nigeria according to Yerima (2006) is soaked in legends, and preserved by folklore. Begho (1996) asserts that the masquerade group of dances constitutes not only the 'focal of divergence' of different entities and planes of existence, it is also the 'locus-focus' of convergence for disparate but related life forms and forces in a people's worldview. The presence of masquerades could therefore suggest more than is overtly depicted; if anything they operate from several symbolic levels that make them able to communicate with people at several points and levels, literally and symbolically. Begho observes that the high respect accorded to masquerades in African communities, the secrecy and taboos surrounding them, and the rituals embodied in their performances more than justify this suggestion and their undoubted theatricality. He notes that in the Yoruba society, there are myths that assert that the gods invented, perfected, and introduced the arts of dance, music and singing to the world through their representatives—the masquerades (ibid.). Begho believes that as a direct result of these god dances, other dances- such as the *Shongo* dance of Yoruba people evolved for various purposes.

Ukaegbu (2007) observes that the history of traditional Igbo dances can be traced to *Mmonwu*, the father of Igbo masquerade which shares the aesthetic features of other well-known Igbo dance. Not surprisingly the Igbo like other African societies have numerous dances that derive specifically from or for the gods. Yet by contrast some Igbo dances were created as a result of important social happenings in a particular historical period. For example, the *Alija* dance of the Owerri people in Eastern Nigeria celebrated the arrival of a new-born baby, and the *Agborogu* dance of the Mbaise people of the same region, was created as a part of a funeral ceremony for people who were deemed sufficiently old before they died. As Kwakwa (1998, p.285) claims 'traditional African dances do not occur in isolation. They often have specific roles within an event or a complex of events organized for a specific occasion'.

In Igbo society, there are dances that are based on occupational activities with well-defined economic, social and political references; for example, the women's *Uri-ukwu* and *Agbachaa-ekuru-nwa* of the Mbaise people in the Owerri region which are based on the relationship between a mid-wife and pregnant woman in labour. Also, the *Nkwaumuagbogho* dance of the Afikpo people is based on

masculinity and wrestling respectively. Rudolf Von Laban (1976, p.3) asserts:

Dances at all times have had a profound connection with the working habits of the period in which they were created. Many dances depict human activities in the economic, social and political circumstances of their times.

Pearl Primus affirms that ‘African traditional dance has urgency. The dancer has direction and purpose. The purpose is to communicate’ (1996, p. 5). African traditional dance is undoubtedly a vital means of communicating the cultural values in a particular society. Their sacred archetypes like rituals everywhere contain the seeds, contexts, myths, and conventions that provide the basis for their contemporary variations. The history of religious and archetypal models or ritual-induced dances shows that most African traditional dances started as ways of leaving everyday life behind and climbing into the realm of the spirit. On the religious functions of African traditional dance, Kwabena Bame (1991, p.18) points out:

If there is any activity, which is a prerequisite to African traditional religion, it is the broad activity of the drumming, singing, and dancing. It is an indispensable element of African

religious worship, the Africans’ process of communion with sports, the lesser gods as well as with God, the Supreme Being, through the pouring of libation, invocation, prayers and trances.

A Ghanaian example of African religious dance is the Akan Akom dance. This is a series of dances performed to enable the priests of Abosom (deity) to work themselves into or release themselves from trances or characteristic states for communicating with deities. In the past, some African traditional dances served courtship purposes. Some social dances in the Cross River state of Nigeria are platforms for courtship between men and women. According to Oko-Offoboche:

The ‘Moni – Nkim’ dance of northern Cross River, the ‘Nkuho’ dance of the Efik, the Mbopo dance of the Ibibios, all maiden dances of South East Nigeria are examples of courtship purposes which dance plays (1996, p. 6).

Traditionally the named dances were staged as part of rites of passage, in this case the growth and maturing from girl to woman and were the various communities’ ways of announcing that the women participants were old enough to marry. In some communities men also had such dances that announced their maturity to

manhood and membership of adult societies such as *Ekpe* and *Okonko* in the Igbo-speaking states of Nigeria. An example of a courtship dance which young men and women show themselves off, thus encouraging courtship is the *Nkwa-Umuagbogho* of Afikpo in the Ebonyi state in Eastern Nigeria. This particular performance belongs to a wider social celebration whose other parts are rarely performed. It consists of young girls in Afikpo, an important town and culture in Northern Igbo society, and began as a traditional dance in honour of the hero of a wrestling contest. The courtship function is unmistakable in both the sensuality of the dancers and the actions of the potential suitors, who exhibit their wrestling prowess and physical and material endowments publically before the dancing girls. As Enekwe points out, The presence of girls during such contests encouraged the boys to put in their best..., on the other hand, the girls got an opportunity for interested persons to apply for marriage [...] (Enekwe, 1991, p. 15).

Perhaps the single largest category of traditional African dances is the group termed ceremonial. The prologue and epilogue of harvest seasons in Africa (the season of yam in Igbo society in Nigeria, for example) are noted for dance festivities featuring various types of

masquerades and non-masquerade dances, most of which entail animal sacrifices and food offerings to earth and water gods. The Orlu community in the Imo state of Nigeria customarily reserved the *Igba-ndi-Eze* dance for coronation and conferment of chieftaincy titles. The dancers are costumed like Ezes (traditional kings), court attendants, and ministers or chiefs. This is an effortless movement-based dance performed on royal occasions or providing entertainment in an Eze's palace. Apart from the ceremonial dances like *Igba-ndi-Eze*, there are varieties of traditional dances in Igbo land and other parts of Africa. Primus, in her description of the nature and versatility of African dance, states that 'the dance is strong magic, the dance is a spirit. It turns the body to liquid steel. It makes it vibrate like a guitar' (1996, p.5). Robert Farris Thompson supports the spiritual and magical nature of African dance:

If Spirits challenge gravity by moving on stilts twelve feet in the air to dance rhythms in the forest of Liberia, if athletes in Nigeria can carry nearly a hundred pounds of carved wood and shoulder this burden for a quarter of an hour while dancing before their king; if Dahomean initiate into a society honouring the collective ancestral dead spin and spin... until the very concept of human dizziness begins to lose its force then anything is possible (1974, p.14).

In Africa, dances portray occupations such as farming, weaving, fishing and hunting. In Nigeria, for example, Emeka Nwabuoku observes that ‘work movements ultimately become the movement of dance’ (1984, p. 22). According to Nwabuoku, the Birnin Kebbi people have many dances based on the movements and gestures of fishing and farming, their main occupation. One dance concerns the movement of fishermen on the river.

In Igbo society, like other parts of Africa some of the dances that this study investigates display occupational and entertainment motifs. Examples are the *Iri-Agha* (war dance) and *Nkwa-Umuagbogho* (maiden dance). Commenting on this, Kalu Okpi (interviewed on the 13th February, 2018) notes that different age groups in Ohafia and Abam are assigned specific tasks, and that their group dances reflect their primary occupations, for example, warriors, entertainers, farmers and hunters. Supporting Okpi’s view, Onwuliri (2011, p.121) adds that in Igbo land ‘warriors are also a guild of professionals in the traditional society. Hence their dance too is occupational or vocational’. The warriors’ guild has its own kind of music and dance in different parts of Igbo society of which archetypal *Iri-Agha* is

the most famous example. Akunna defines two categories of African dance, the secular and religious, observing:

The secular dance is believed to have come into beings, as an expression of subjective feelings of an ecstatic nature which afterwards was secularised and became social dance. The religious dance is believed to have been emanated from magic ceremonies and cults with religious imperatives (2006, p. 93).

Yerima (2006) supports Akunna’s view on the classification of Nigerian traditional dances claiming that in Nigeria ritual dances are deeply rooted in religious activities. Dancers were incorporated into religious worship and religious ceremonies to evoke or worship the gods—the main dancers performing as well as doubling as the guiding fathers and mothers of such cults within any given society. Some ritual dances were accompanied by ritual sacrifices and songs, as for in the procession of the *Iri-Agha* dance of the Avu-Owerri people in eastern Nigeria that is performed for the yearly cleansing of evil and malevolent forces from the community.

Social dances, on the other hand, were less serious in content and form (Yerima, 2006). Although there were also specific occasions on which they were performed, social dances were

usually purely celebratory in nature; they include dances presented as part of naming ceremonies, the celebration of someone's elevation to a high status within a community or marriage. According to Begho (1996), this subdivision contains the following categories: harvest, festival, heroic, funeral, coronation and traditional title dances. Archetypal *Iri-Agha* dance theatre falls under the heroic dance category. This consists of war dances designed to dispel fear in potential male combatants in a community and to prepare them physically and psychologically for action and victory dances which seek to re-enact the ferocity of renowned warriors in war, either as a kind of imitative rite to ensure victory or a kind of jubilation for achievements won through prowess in war. Significantly, Nigerian traditional dances are used to teach and reinforce cultural patterns. Many groups have dances which ridicule through gesture, movement, song, and music for those guilty of offensive behaviours such as theft, political brigade, incest, rape, marital infidelity and abuse, promiscuity, etc. The dancers may be cast in masquerade form or their bodies are temporarily possessed by a supernatural entity, and thus they can perform with freedom from 'libel' or other retribution (Hanna, 1973). Family obligations are one of the most frequently communicated themes in African traditional dance. Among the Owerri

and Mbaise people in Nigeria, the birth of a child is celebrated, and men and women who have many children are praised. In the greater Owerri area comprising the Mbaise, Ikeduru and Mbaitoli communities, one of these dances specifically celebrates a woman who has given birth to ten sons as a great social status symbol. Religious traditions, achievement, status and economic patterns are communicated through dance. In some areas, people dance to honour those in higher positions. In others such as Onitsha in Nigeria, the king is required to dance before his people at the annual yam feast to retain his position of honour. As stated earlier many African peoples have dances that mime traditional occupational behaviour important to the local economy. Such dances serve as media for giving work instructions and providing practice in the various movements essential to routine work activities. The traditional dances in Nigeria from which contemporary dance practices grew, have a long tradition of festivals, storytelling and masquerade performances. African dancers and choreographers are able to work from these traditions in creating a new platform for contemporary dance in their society. Therefore dance plays a vital role in determining the direction of contemporary dance in Africa. However, the various traditional Nigerian/African traditional explained above

were operating only at the communities and states level. The need to celebrate those unifying aspects of the dances led to the establishment of the National Troupe of Nigeria, a creative organ which could enhance such cultural celebration and help to unify this country.

The National Troupe of Nigeria

The idea for establishing the national troupe of Nigeria was made manifest during the second world black and African festival of art and culture in 1977 in Lagos, Nigeria. The proposal for Nigeria, the giant of Africa, to have a national troupe of its own was concretized when the Nigerian cultural officers at FESTAC said the creative importance and cultural significance of the national assembles and troupes of other smaller African countries such as Guinea, Ghana and Senegal. Yerima obseves that:

Even South African which was not then unified and freed country because of the then practice of apartheid system, still bought the dance troupe, Ipi tombi, which though not officially the national troupe of South Africa still serves as the troupe with the unified national aspirations of the majority of the people of South Africa (2003, p.136).

After FESTAC 1977, formal president Olusegun Obasanjo as the head of state of the then federal military government created the parastatal known as the national troupe of Nigeria. He also created the federal ministry of culture and tourism as the supervising body to oversee the activities of the national troupe of Nigeria. And this is seen as major pointer towards the realization of the importance of culture and tourism in the modern economic and social development of Nigeria in the new millennium.

The national troupe saw the need for a multi cultural society to come together and form a very strong troupe at the centre which could enhance cultural development and be a revenue generating avenue for government. The national troupe of Nigeria was formally commissioned to go on a nation-wide tour and recruit artiste through auditions, a new set of artistes that would now form the core-artistes of the national troupe. Chief Hubert Ogunde was in the process of training these artiste when he died in April 1990 . Still aware of the importance of the national troupe, President Ibrahim Babangida signed into law decree 47 of 29 October 1991, titled "National Theatre and the National Troupe of Nigeria". Mr Bayo Oduneye was appointed the second artistic director.

The decree laid out the following objectives for the national troupe:

- a. Encourage the discovery and development of talents in the performing arts.
- b. Achieve high artistic productions specifically designed for national and international troupe
- c. Ensure that productions of the troupe are geared towards national aspirations
- d. Encourage the development of children's theatre
- e. Ensure the preservation of the repertoire of the troupe

In the representations of these troupes of various states, dramatic performances, dance and indeed, art has shown its importance in making significant contributions not only to the national identity of Nigeria, but also to its socio-cultural and political development. Therefore, The national troupe of Nigeria as the name implies has the responsibility to discover artistic people of our cultural manifestations in the performing arts to create works of high artistic standards for both national and international consumption.

Integrating Ethnic Dances and Dancers into the National Troupe

The formation of what later became the National Troupe of Nigeria started with Chief Hubert Ogunde. According to Edward Gondo,

one of the foremost artist invited by Chief Hubert Ogunde for the Ososa experiment, he states:

The federal government Nigerian, through the federal department of culture, invited various traditional groups to honour international invitation to perform at festivals or international trade expose such as the Edinburgh festival in the United Kingdom. The sole administrator of culture Colonel Tunde Akogun and his officers such as Dan Awodoye, invited the late Chief Hubert Ogunde to start what was later to be known as the Osasa experiment in 1986. (Interviewed on the 17th April, 2018).

The experiment was to bring together a group of artiste from various states of the federation, train them and present them as the first sets of artistes for the new national dance troupe for Edinburgh festival and this troupe later became the national troupe of Nigeria. After the death of Chief Hubert Ogunde, the management staff of the national troupe led by Mr Bayo Oduneye (the Artistic Director) started to invite artistes from different states Arts Councils.

Most ethnic/traditional dances are housed in the state Council for Arts and Culture. The national troupe sent for at least three artistes representing the states Arts Council for audition. Normally, auditions are carried out

bi-annually with the aim of selecting and developing artistes from the state Arts Council in order to enhance the quality of performance and presentation styles at the states' level upon the return of these artiste. Such exercise has gone a long way in developing the quality of dance performance and in fanning the embers of unity in Nigeria.

The integration of ethnic/traditional dances and dancers into the national troupe had been very successful. From the auditioning stage, the artiste from the various states are asked to perform their indigenous dances. According to Udoka:

Other indices for determining the success or otherwise of the artiste include mental tasks to test their recall abilities, imagination, physical expression and body type. The auditions do not consider religion or ethnic origin of the artistes (2005, p.335).

After the audition, the selected artistes that are representing their various state Arts Councils are promoted to a new rank by one grade level (based of Civil Service secondment regulation). National troupe has not recorded any conflict, tension or disagreement based on religious or ethnic differences. Rather, artiste from different states accepts each other as fellow Nigerians and appreciate the opportunity given to them by the federal

government through the national troupe to learn more about other ethnic societies and their arts. The researcher observes that these artistes start and end rehearsals or performance with either Islamic or Christian prayers. Moreover, they all lived in the same camp and share rooms without religious or ethnic considerations, whatsoever.

The dance training and orientation of dancers in the national troupe helps to foster unity, creating a versatile and cultural knowledge of other ethnic groups accross Nigeria. So the theoretical and intellectual training are designed to disabuse the minds of the dancers from different states which hitherto held to ethnic loyalties. To accualise this, the troupe had to teach different histories and practices of ethnic dances accross the geo-political zones in Nigeria. The dancers are also thought patterns of other cultures and therefore made it possible for artists to understand and appreciate the cultural ethos of others with whom they share a constitutional family. In an interview (on the 20th April, 2018) with Emmanuel Adejumo, a core artiste of the national troupe, he asserts that the dancers approach these ethnic dances with respect to the cultures that evolved the dances and by extension become capable of speaking the language of other ethnic groups.

Conclusion

Ahmed Yerima, the former artistic director of national troupe of Nigeria asserts:

It must be stated categorically, that the national troupe, in terms of its contributions to economic and social development of Nigeria, must be looked at from the products that it has to offer. Well packaged and beautifully rehearsed aspects of Nigeria's cultural heritage in the expressive forms and gestures of dance, music and drama (2003, p.138).

The national troupe celebrates the cultural heritage of Nigeria, hence the reason why they themselves are called the cultural ambassadors of Nigeria. Integrating the ethnic dance at the national level has created a possible revenue generating arm of Nigerian government. It also serves as a propaganda arm that federal government uses from time to time in servicing bilateral relations with other countries, it can also be used to disseminate information and government policies to the citizens. The national troupe of Nigeria performs at Independent Day celebration and at the reception of foreign dignitaries.

Therefore, there is no gainsaying that one indisputable fact is that the strength of nation is in the quality of its culture, and how well that nation tries to preserve and celebrate her

culture and to a great extent, this has been achieved through the integration of the states troupes, their dances and other forms of arts and culture into the national troupe of Nigeria.

References

- Akunna, G. I. (2006) Expression of Womanhood in Modern Nigerian Dance Forms. In: Yerima, A., Rasaki, B. and Udoka, A. (eds.) *Critical Perspectives on Dance in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Kraft Books Limited, pp. 110-123.
- Bame, K. (1991) *Profiles in African Traditional Popular Culture: Consensus and Conflict: Dance, Drama, Festival and Funerals*. New York: Clear Type Press Inc.
- Begho, F. (1996) Traditional African Dance in Context. In: Kariamu W. A. (ed.) *African Dance: An Artistic, Historical and Philosophical Inquiry*. Eritrea: Africa World Press Inc., pp. 163-182.
- Enekwe, O. (1991) *Theories in Dance in Nigeria*. Nsukka: Afa Press.
- Hanna, J. (1973) African Dance: The Continuity of Change. *Yearbook of the International Folk Music Council*, Vol. 5, pp. 165-174.
- Kwakwa, P. A. (1998) Dance in Communal Life. In: Rull, M. S. (ed.) *The Garland Encyclopaedia of World Music*. New York: Garland Publication Inc. pp. 282-285.
- Okoro – Offoboche, E. (1996) *The ABC Dance Art*. Calabar: Uptriko Press Sheets.

Primus, P. (1996) African Dance. In: Kariam W. A. (ed.) *African Dance: An Artistic, Historical and Philosophical Inquiry*. Eritrea: Africa World Press Inc., pp. 3-11.

Thompson, R. (1974) *African Art in Motion*, UCLA Arts Council. California: University of California Press.

Ukaegbu, V. (2007) *The Use of Masks in Igbo Theatre in Nigeria: The Aesthetic Flexibility of Performance Traditions*. Lewiston: Edwin Mellen Press.

Yerima, A. (2006) Nigeria Traditional Dancers: History and Practice. In: Yerima, A., Rasaki, B. and Udoka, A. (eds.) *Critical Perspectives on Dance in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Kraft Books Limited, pp. 17-44.

..... (2003) *Fragmented Thoughts and Specifics: Essays in Dramatic Literature*. Ikeja: Booksplus Nigerian Limited.

Interviews

Kalu Okpi, one of Nigeria's foremost dance professionals, cultural commentators and former Director of the Abia State Council for Arts and Culture, Umuahia interviewed on the 13th February, 2018.

Edward Gondo, one of the foremost artist invited by Chief Hubert Ogunde for the Osoa experiment. Interviewed on the 17th April, 2018.

Emmanuel Adejumo a staff and core artiste of the national troupe of Nigeria interviewed on the 20th April, 2018.